

**STUDY OF QUALITY OF REFLECTION IN STUDENTS
TEACHERS PROFESSIONAL THINKING**

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Abstract-

This research paper studies the quality of reflection in student teachers professional thinking at District Institute of Education and Training (DIET). The teacher training is to fulfill the basic learning needs of all the school environment bridging social and gender gaps with the active participation of the community. The programme aims at preparing teachers for elementary stage of education. A supreme effort of quality is needed on a high priority basis, to improve the situation of academic, administrative and professional development of teacher training institution. The teacher training is sufficiently realized that courses for professional subjects contain development of student teacher language proficiency, intelligence and personality. It also provides a strong support to the student teacher training. The student teacher reflection will indicate the priorities to be adopted the different courses of educational opportunities .

Keyword-

District Institute of Education and Training (DIET), Professional Development, Reflection of Professional Development.

Introduction-

The national policy on education recognized the continuity and inseparability of teacher training institution and recommended permanent educational mechanisms for it. Teaching-learning material and aids, library facilities, quality development programme is essential in

teacher training institution i.e. student teacher training has acquired an important position for the improvement in the quality of teachers. The student's teacher to build up professional knowledge and skills, but also encourage reflection professional thinking. Student teacher acquired a knowledge and skills in their subject teaching, training practical, co curricular and personality development programme. Self satisfaction and reflection after teaching supervision session in various activity conducted in teacher training institution. Quality reflection is considered to be crucial to the development process of student teachers (Hershkowitz & Schwarz, 1999). According to the schema theory of learning (Anderson, 2005), an individual constructs a mental model on the issue of concern based on prior experience of the self. In line with this thought, researchers in the field of teacher education suggest that the opportunities for student teachers to engage in self reflection after field experience activities enable them to construct their own mental model of teaching practices, based on their field experiences. In a situation like the present when new and dynamic methods of instruction are needed such as attitude becomes an obstacle to progress in teacher training. It can be modified only by effective professional development which will initiate the teachers to the needed reevaluation in teaching and lay the foundations for their future professional growth.

The essence of teacher training is quality and in its absence teacher education becomes not only financial waste but a source of overall deterioration in educational standards. Highest importance to this teacher training of qualitative improvement. Existing programmes of teacher training are largely tradition .rigid and divorced from the realities of schools and existing programmes of educational reconstruction.

Objectives-

- 1.To study the quality of various activity of students teacher. .
- 2.To know the knowledge and skill acquired by students teacher.
- 3.To study the various changes in curriculum suggested by students teacher.
4. To study the reflection quality of reflection in students teachers profession.

Methodology-

In this research study, survey method was adopted to study the reflection Quality of Reflection in Students Teachers Professional thinking. The questionnaires were structured on student's teacher in District Institute of Education and Training, Kolhapur. Quality about teacher profession and open-ended questionnaire. Analysis plan was prepared and with statistical inputs analysis was done.

Sample-

The stratification has been done on the basis the reflection quality of reflection in students teachers professional thinking. The impact of training on students teacher pre service training. For the present study the purposive sampling method was used for the selection of the sample consisted of 74 students teacher District Institute of Education and Training, Kolhapur .

Analysis –

Table No 1: The reflection quality of reflection in students teachers professional thinking.

Sr.No.	Details	No.of students	Percentage
1	Knowledge	53	71.62
2	Curriculum Development	52	70.27
3	Curriculum Planning	51	68.92
4	School life events	24	32.43
5	Course duration	56	75.68
6	Learning difficulties	70	94.59

7	Emotional Insecurity	69	93.24
8	Self satisfaction	65	87.84
9	Forgetting	45	60.81
10	Feeling	42	56.76
11	Social Atmosphere	35	47.30
12	Evaluation	45	60.81
13	Internship	62	83.78
14	Student –teacher Interaction	25	33.78
15	Classroom management	63	85.14
16	Discipline	55	74.32
17	Action Research	54	72.97
18	Work experience	56	75.68
19	Remedial teaching	48	64.86
20	Report writing	63	85.14
21	Management of co curricular activity	65	87.84

Graph shows reflection quality of reflection in student's teacher's professional thinking

Observation:

The above table and graph shows 87.84% Students-teacher not satisfied in teaching-learning materials and Aids. The equipment and materials should be suitable and sufficient in quality and quantity for the variety of activities planned in the teacher training. 94.59% student-teacher not satisfied with Functional and appropriate furniture in required number for instructional and other purposes. Reorientation in the subject knowledge and skill of teacher-educators should be done in collaboration with competency of NGO's and where necessary with arts and science colleges.75.68%be a carefully planned content course which would include a study of fundamental concepts and their implication for the school syllabus and of the textbooks and source materials to assists teaching at the school stage.70.27% students-teacher suggest there should be provision in the teacher –training levels for a study of the subjects to be taught in depth as well as range.

Conclusion-

Each teacher -training institution should work out a detailed scheme involving university department, colleges, schools, other teacher-training institution including the use of their laboratories and libraries. Re-orientation course in subject knowledge should be closely related to the special techniques and methods used in teaching the subject concerned. Set lesson plans with emphasis on rigid provides general support to the teachers, whereas it carries a definite part of the curriculum to the students at regular intervals. Time should also be found to orientate student's teacher attitudes to the significance and possibilities of the profession that they have chosen to awaken sensitiveness to the human factors involved and to stress the social values of educational development. An attempt should be made to develop the students-teacher maturity through contacts.

Suggestion –

To provide the new methods of teaching and improvement in methods of teaching and evaluation. Developing research and evolving better curricula and techniques of teaching. To organize interaction between students –teacher and other teacher training students –teacher in summer courses in subject content as well as in professional development. Creating appropriate agencies both at the centre and in the states for the maintenance of standards in professional development of students- teachers. The organization of practice-teaching to reiterate that in keeping with the goals of education in a modern society, the emphasis in practice – teaching and in courses on methods and materials should be on developing the problem solving abilities of students-teacher using assimilation and understanding of fundamental facts only as a basis. Monitoring and Evaluation Procedures for quality Education.

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